

Table 2. Rice cultivars screened for adverse-soil tolerance. IRRI, 1976.

Source	Rice cultivars (no.) screened for					
	Salinity	Alkalinity	Iron toxicity	Organic soils	Zinc deficiency	Phosphorus deficiency
Germ plasm bank	1446	1338	12	0	5918	1134
General breeding program	1020	2397	108	195	850	330
Specific hybrids	2059	676	0	0	0	0
Total	4525	4411	120	195	6768	1464

Four IR4630 and IR4763 lines showed high salt tolerance; IR30, IR32, IR36, and 13 advanced breeding lines had moderate tolerance. IR4227-28-3 and IR4227-104-3 revealed high tolerance for alkalinity and 52 advanced breeding lines showed moderate tolerance. IR20, IR34, BG90-2, and several elite lines tolerated zinc deficiency. IR20, IR29, IR32, and many elite lines from the crosses

IR2031, IR2070, IR2071, and IR2153 manifested tolerance for iron toxicity. IR28, IR29, IR30, IR34, IR1514A-E666, and several IR2061 lines tolerated phosphorus deficiency.

Several IR varieties and many IRRI elite lines with good agronomic characteristics and resistance to diseases and insects showed tolerance to adverse soils even though no conscious effort had been made to achieve it. ❧

of observation. The other originally healthy plants showed disease symptoms after the third or fourth week.

The studies suggest, in addition to stubble burning, the following control measures: (1) control of weeds and volunteer rice, (2) dikes and banks to prevent river overflow onto fields, and (3) clean cultivation and early roguing of diseased plants. ❧

Possible presence of bacterial blight in Latin America

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Bacterial blight had not been previously reported in America. During my visit to rice farms in Panama on 5 and 6 August 1976 and in Ecuador on 10 and 11 August, I observed some rice showing symptoms of the disease, and several weeds with similar symptoms. On 12 August I forwarded a report of my observations to the directors general of the International Center of Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) and the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI). What follows is excerpted from the report.

On a rice farm of the Bayano project of the Panama government, CR1113, a variety newly selected from an IRRI line in Costa Rica, was about to flower. Small and large patches of blighted upper leaves, similar to those seen in bacterial blight in the early stage of an epidemic, were seen near edges of the farm. Close examination revealed the characteristic symptoms of the disease. Nearby roadside colonies of a common noxious weed *Manisuris* sp. likewise showed symptoms. Bacterial blight symptoms were also found in patches on a second farm planted to CICA 6. There *Manisuris* sp. and colonies of wild rice *Oryza latifolia* were also infected, some severely. Blighted patches were found on a third farm planted to Nilo 1; nearby *Manisuris* sp. and *O. latifolia* were infected. More disease was found on a seed-multiplication farm for possible new varieties bred locally between IR8 and Nilo 1; a great deal of *Manisuris* sp. nearby was severely infected, as was a weed locally called "Cabezona." A large sage with triangular

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Ufra disease spread by water flow

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In Irrawaddy Delta, Burma, ufra disease of rice caused by the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* is associated with lowlands onto which rivers overflow because of tidal action. Field observations showed the following sources of the disease inoculum: (1) the wild rice *Oryza perennis*, growing along banks of waterways, its roots in mud and its tops above water surface; (2) *O. meyeriana*; (3) *Leersia hexandra*; and (4) volunteer rice plants.

On a healthy rice plant grown in a pot with a diseased plant, especially in open air in the rainy season, chlorotic leaves appear in 2 weeks, suggesting that water is the agent of disease spread. The following experiment showed dispersal along currents.

In a 100-m canal, 30 cm wide and 18 cm deep (see figure), water was put in and drained at the rate of about 1 liter/minute. One group of 10 C4-63 rice plants with ufra disease and four groups of healthy plants were placed in the canal at 20-m intervals.

The upstream group of plants remained healthy throughout 10 weeks

Plan of an experiment to test the transmission of ufra disease of rice through paddy water.